

Perceptions of Citizens over the 'smart city' Brussels

A qualitative study through 'walkshops'

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1. Introduction

In January and February 2022, a total of five workshops were held in the centre of Brussels: four with citizens, and one with smart city staff of the city of Brussels administration. The aims of the workshops were twofold: (1) citizen responses to the collection of personal data in public space and feeding those back to smart city administrators, and (2) to further evaluate the utility of the workshop as a tool for citizen engagement in the assessment of smart city risks, potentially as part of legally required Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs).

As a low-threshold, interactive method, workshops can also function as an informal survey of citizens' perceptions of decision-making around the introduction of new technologies in the city.

This document reports on our findings: which topics came up among the workshop participants, and can such workshops provide useful input for decision-making processes in smart cities? We first describe the methodology (section 2), and how it was tested and implemented in practice, including a description of the participants (section 3). We subsequently present our findings from the workshops with citizen participants (section 4). Results from a methodology evaluation survey held after the workshops will be presented in section 5, followed by a discussion and some preliminary conclusions (section 6).

Previously, workshops were conducted in Leuven and Ghent ([reports available in Dutch](#)). The workshops in Brussels are the last to be held with citizens. The conclusions presented in this report are preliminary to the extent that they have not yet been combined with the results from Leuven and Ghent, and they have yet to be validated in interviews with a wider group of smart city administrators. The conclusions presented here are therefore only descriptive of what we have found in Brussels.

2. Methodology

Workshops consist of 1.5-hour walks in a city centre with a maximum number of ten participants, led by (two) researchers or facilitators. The discussion during the walks is centred around citizens' experiences with and perceptions of the collection and processing of (personal) data in public space.

The researchers or facilitators share information about the smart city concept, the various sensors encountered during the walk, and general data protection concepts. Workshops lead past a variety of technologies that process personal data, specifically different types of CCTV cameras, cell phone towers, parking sensors, ANPR cameras, public Wi-Fi hotspots, Bluetooth, and Wi-Fi trackers. Citizens are asked about their information needs regarding these technologies, and the conversation is guided in such a way that different perspectives, i.e. advantages as well as disadvantages of data processing activities for different groups of citizens, can be discussed.

While the walks themselves last about an hour to an hour and a half (respecting a natural flow of the conversation), the last 30-45 minutes of the workshops are dedicated to wider discussion of citizen perceptions and an evaluation of the workshop, including a short anonymous paper survey.

As the processing of personal data in public space may easily give rise to uncomfortable feelings of 'surveillance', the workshop discussions are not video or audio recorded. Instead, assistants make notes of the conversations, leaving participants unidentified; participants are given a sticker with a number to attach to their coats, for reference in the notes.

Square Rogier, Brussels

3. Implementation

The workshop route in Brussels was designed in close collaboration with the Brussels Regional Informatics Centre (BRIC/ CIBG /CIRB). The enthusiasm of this organisation was a strong support for us in setting up this walk. The BRIC also provided contacts at the city of Brussels and the largest Dutch library of Brussels, Muntpunt, for distribution of the workshop information to citizens, as well as an online registration form.

It is important to note that the methodology was refined in an iterative process of testing, evaluating, and adapting, which took place in Brussels from July 2021 onwards. To identify a route, several online meetings were conducted with two representatives of BRIC, who also joined for an informal test walk. Later, more representatives of the organisation were invited for a "friendly user walk". This proved to be extremely useful to get additional insights and expert knowledge about the contents of the walk as well as early feedback.

The test phase also evaluated two different approaches: (1) facilitator-led or (2) free-floating walks. From this test phase, we can conclude that the latter approach only works if participants are already knowledgeable enough to recognise sensors, and their purposes and affordances. This approach would not work for the general population. Since one of our goals is to develop workshops as a mechanism for citizen involvement in Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA), we chose to remain with the facilitator-led format.

Route and contents

The workshops in Brussels started at Rogier square in the city centre, a central hub for transportation in the middle of a business district. This space is monitored by a multitude of cameras, installed, or controlled by several organisations: the city police, the city administration, hotels, a bank, administrative offices of the European Commission, and the public transportation system.

The workshop route in Brussels
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This environment is the conversation starter; about consent or other legal grounds for processing personal data as mentioned in the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), public interests (e.g. public safety) and private interests (e.g. security and theft prevention), and legal requirements for information provision. In the conversations during the walk, the researchers actively looked for different perspectives, that is, both advantages and disadvantages, from the points of view of different groups of city dwellers.

From Rogier square, the route leads through a subway station, a shopping mall, and a shopping street, ending at a public square in front of the Muntpunt library. On the way, the group passes a variety of technologies that process personal data: more cameras, but also public Wi-Fi hotspots, access gates to the public transport system, cell phone towers, sensors that count passers-by (both Wi-Fi and Bluetooth-based), smart dustbins, e-scooters, smart light posts, and the municipal app Fix my Street. After about an hour the walk ends and another half-hour discussion was held and the workshop was evaluated with the participants. At the end of the workshops, the participants completed a short evaluation form.

Participants and context

The four workshops with citizens took place on Monday, 24 January (12:00-14:00), Tuesday, 1 February (12:00-14:00), and Sunday, 6 February (11:00-13:00 and 15:00-17:00). The first two workshops were conducted in Dutch, the other two were planned to be conducted in

French, to reflect the bilingualism of the city of Brussels. However, at the last walk mainly Dutch speakers were present, and the workshop was conducted in that language, with informal English translations for the two non-Dutch speaking participants. Consequently, only one of the four walks was conducted in French.

For the first workshop on Monday, there were six participants, who, for the most part, turned out to be very knowledgeable on the topic of technologies in public space. The workshop on Tuesday, 1 February, saw eleven participants. On the morning of Sunday 6 February, conditions were stormy, and only one fifth of registered participants (four individuals) showed up. In the afternoon of that same day, there were seven participants. Participants' age categories varied from young children to retired citizens, although participants were predominantly middle-aged, white, well-educated, and well-spoken. Many participants displayed relatively advanced knowledge of and interest in the topics discussed. In the first group, the participants had professional knowledge related to the topics. They often expressed nuanced opinions and engaged in a polite conversation. The interaction was such that opinions that deviated from the majority could also be expressed.

Smart Dustbin in Brussels

After the citizen walks, the findings were shared with smart city decision-makers from the city of Brussels, during a final workshop on February 9th. Five city officials joined this walk.

4. Results

Cameras and perceptions of surveillance

As in previous workshops in Ghent and Leuven, cameras provoked much discussion among the participants in Brussels. Cameras are prevalent along the workshop route and are, according to participants, also the most eye-catching data processing technology during the walk.

"It is hard to see how one small camera can be a bother, but the sheer number ...! There are streets in Brussels where you cannot walk without being filmed."

Several participants stated that even though they may have been generally aware of cameras in public space they did not pay much attention to them before in their daily lives. They were therefore surprised by just how many cameras there are along the route in Brussels.

"I am surprised by the number of cameras I see now. I come here often and I haven't paid attention to that."

Many participants told personal stories about their experiences with camera monitoring. One participant recalled how her bike was stolen in a camera-monitored subterranean parking, but the police did not do anything with the camera footage and the bike was not recovered. Similarly, another participant said that available camera footage could not be used to recover her stolen smartphone. Yet another explained how cameras were installed in his

neighbourhood to monitor illegal dumping, but despite registering hundreds of cases, nothing was done with those insights. A fourth participant recalled a murder case at the Ninoofsepoort in Brussels that happened while cameras were turned off, remarking that people have a false expectation that cameras offer solutions in these cases. There was also recurrent discussion of the relative merits of fake cameras as deterrence, and of function creep¹.

The perceived futility of camera monitoring seems to have given rise to negative attitudes. Comparisons were made with dystopian science fiction and state surveillance in the People's Republic of China. Several participants expressed discomfort with ubiquitous monitoring and a concern that "it is getting worse".

"I may be of a different generation, but this reminds me of A Brave New World or Big Brother. Also being filmed everywhere. Young people think that is normal, but to me it feels uncomfortable."

To counterbalance a downward spiral of negativity, facilitators questioned participants on potential benefits of or conditions for acceptable camera monitoring.

For example, participants generally agreed camera monitoring can reduce traffic violations and support the enforcement of low emission zones. In another example, when a participant mentioned that cameras filming cashiers in shops invade those employees' privacy, the facilitator pointed out that theft prevention is a legitimate interest of shop owners, and another participant told about a situation in which a cashier gave her incorrect change but camera footage could prove how much she had paid.

The anecdote provoked a discussion on the substantiation of 'legitimate interests'², with participants advancing the idea that there should be clear criteria for the validity of arguments to underpin legitimate interests like theft prevention, e.g. crime statistics.

¹ Function creep is a about the gradual widening of the use of a technology or system beyond the purpose for which it was originally intended, esp when this leads to potential invasion of privacy.

² Data controllers invoking legitimate interests as the lawful ground for a data processing activity need to conduct a 'legitimate interest assessment', in which the substantiated necessity and effectivity of their methods are balanced against the level of privacy intrusion for data subjects.

More transparency was another condition that was mentioned for higher acceptance of camera monitoring (more on transparency below). One participant suggested publishing a map of all cameras in a given area, such as a shopping mall.

Referring to an incident in the Brussels subway in January 2022, when security camera footage was leaked of a man pushing a woman onto the tracks, several participants felt that the public interest in the distribution of such image's trumps privacy concerns for the people involved.³ Specifically, the public interest the participants identified was a stark warning not to stand too close to the tracks.

Smartphone data and commercial purposes

Crowd measurement was discussed in relation to cameras and other technologies. This sort of data processing activity has become prevalent in cities, especially since the COVID-19 pandemic. Topics of discussion were, for instance, whether cameras are a proportional means for the purpose of crowd measurement or if less intrusive technologies would be preferred.

Along the route, in the shopping mall City 2, Bluetooth tracking was encountered and discussed. Participants were generally less aware of this technology than of cameras. During the second workshop, two participants started discussing adapting the MAC addresses of their phones in order to remain anonymous. Other participants wondered whether Bluetooth tracking can be used for targeted advertising, and whether the police can get access to personal data collected via this sort of sensor. A participant interposed that police do not need access to Bluetooth data because location data can be obtained from mobile network providers like Proximus, which offer more insights.

The reuse and reselling of data by mobile network providers such as Proximus, Telenet, or Orange elicited lively discussions. The fact that cities buy such data for city marketing purposes, for instance, was not highly appreciated. Although the facilitators explained that only aggregated, de-identified data are traded, a participant stated the intention to actively opt-out with their provider (Proximus in this case). Participants were also concerned that the combination of different datasets could lead to re-identification of citizens.

The conversation on telecom data led to an interesting discussion on compensation for consumers. A participant remarked that if Proximus makes money off her data, she would also like to profit from that. Other participants concurred. Asked by the facilitator whether being paid for the use of one's data would make that use more acceptable, only one participant replied 'maybe'. Others mentioned conditions: only specific types of data, guarantees on data security, and so on.

On the topic of personal data for sale, one participant explained that the business model of e-scooter services is not (only) to provide mobility but to collect personal data for sale, to the indignation of other participants in that workshop. Another participant pointed out that the same is true for Uber and that one of the e-scooter companies is owned by Google. Participants wondered who would buy mobility data and were surprised to learn that public authorities can be among the buyers.

³ This appears to be in line with the journalistic exemption for the processing of personal data.

Unlike in other cities, several participants mentioned turning off their smartphones when in public space, turning off specific functionalities of their phones (gps, Bluetooth, WiFi), leaving their smartphones home, or using 'dumb' phones, to avoid various types of smartphone tracking (see also the section on citizen empowerment below).

Transparency and feeling informed

Most participants had never paid attention to signs about cameras or other data-processing technologies. For instance, no one had ever noticed the Bluetooth and WiFi tracking signs at the shopping mall, including the smart city administrators (who did show a great deal of interest in the explanation). None of the participants had ever used the contact details on signs to ask questions of data controllers about purposes or other details of the processing. During each walkshop, the facilitators asked whether participants thought they needed to be informed if data were processed about them, and most did not think that was a requirement. We can therefore conclude that most participants were unaware of their right to be informed and none had actively exercised the right to access (GDPR art. 12-15).

Information about Bluetooth and Wi-Fi tracking at the entrance of City2 shopping

"I have never seen those signs about Wi-Fi and Bluetooth tracking. I don't normally pay attention to that. You can't pay attention to all of that, then you can't live anymore. It will also make you paranoid."

A participant suggested information signs should be more clearly visible, for instance by making them bright red. Asked more specifically about the information on signs, some participants were surprised by the mention of controllers' contact details, others were curious about QR codes for further information. Several participants would like to see more information about purposes and retention periods on the signs, perhaps even 'positive news' of what was achieved thanks to the sensor.

One participant mentioned that perhaps they should be more aware of what happens with their personal data, but due to a lack of technical knowledge they would not know how to question responses. Another participant also noted that citizens do not know enough about what happens with their personal data. A third participant suggested the press should play a role in reporting on smart city activities, but they should do so accurately, because in his experience journalists did not always report in a balanced manner.

"I do want to know, but the more I know, the more fear I have. So don't think about it too much, because then you can't participate in society anymore."

Other concerns and attitudes

Though many participants expressed concerns over surveillance or unexpected uses of personal data, the workshop method also allowed an exploration of less common concerns. For instance, one participant thought that smart cities and data-processing technologies culminate in a pollution of public space. Also the general tendency to datafication of everyday life was regarded with concern by some participants. One expressed a feeling that the digital is taking over the social and the human:

“Humanity is being replaced. Civic responsibility is in decline, numbers are taking over.”

Another participant mentioned a fear of being nudged or manipulated based on the data collected about her. Interestingly, the same participant later mentioned feeling positively motivated by information screens along bike lanes displaying the rising number of cyclists (a typical example of a nudge) and cited this type of positive reinforcement as a good example of smart city applications.

On the other hand, a participant explained how she was less concerned about surveillance in public space than about cookies. She perceived online tracking and targeting as more intrusive and unavoidable than the tracking in the shopping mall. Another participant was particularly concerned about the intermingling of private and public interests in smart city applications.

The exclusion of marginalised groups from mobility-as-a-service solutions like e-scooters through geofencing was also briefly discussed.⁴ In one workshop in particular, questions of who benefits from smart city solutions at whose expense came up, for instance homeless people being disproportionately targeted by camera monitoring. In the same group, participants expressed a concern over risks to the right of assembly.

When talking about MOBIB cards⁵, another interesting data processing sensor, participants wondered whether the public transport provider can follow subscribers during the complete time of their travel, and that there can be benefits (for example mobility-as-a-service⁶) but also undesirable consequences for the individual. This illustrated an interesting trade-off: while mobility-as-a-service, for example, could greatly add to the

Rogier Subway Station, Brussels

⁴ This discussion originated in the fact that e-scooter providers in Brussels do not offer their services in certain municipalities, for example Molenbeek. The zone for dropping off the vehicles is geographically limited by a geofence, which is a virtual perimeter for a real-world geographic area.

⁵ MOBIB cards are the long-term subscriptions to the Brussels public transport provider MIVB/STIB.

⁶ Mobility-as-a-service (MaaS) offers multi-modal travel in an integrated and convenient manner for users.

convenience of people travelling the city, this cannot be facilitated without substantial amounts of personal data processed.

Safety and security

Especially in the discussions about cameras, the topic of safety and security came up. Some participants mentioned that cameras promote a ‘false sense of safety’ because there are too many (anecdotal) examples of ineffective use of camera monitoring. Several participants questioned that cameras even contribute to lower feelings of unsafety. One participant asked what ‘unsafe streets’ means, for whom.

However, participants certainly also mentioned positive contributions to safety and security of smart city technologies. A parent mentioned that cameras could help in finding back a lost child. Another participant related how neighbours had managed to prove to their insurance company that thieves had stolen their car thanks to cameras in their street. In the discussion of crowd measurement during COVID-19, participants were relatively positive about how the measurement of crowds can contribute to safety, for instance to support the police or to improve the flow of pedestrians through the city at busy times. Some mentioned that cameras can support “the Me Too Movement”.

“Bluetooth can make things safer perhaps, in crowd measurement.”

Citizen empowerment: rights, agency, and choice

Several participants showed concern over the inescapability of personal data processing, connected to different technologies. One participant said he had stopped using fitness apps because the data may be used by insurance companies. Even if a specific app feels trustworthy when a person starts using it, the app itself or its data may be bought later by less trustworthy market actors. Another participant said it was becoming increasingly difficult to avoid sharing personal data if one still wants to function in society. One participant also mentioned peer pressure, for instance in the use of chat apps.

“If you do not want to share personal data, it gets difficult when you have to accept certain conditions to do something else. There is less and less you can do if you do not accept some things on your phone. Think of ‘Itsme’ and the covid safe ticket app. You are forced to share data.”

Avoiding the use of technology as a way to regain agency and choice was mentioned remarkably more often in Brussels than in other cities. For example, participants mentioned leaving their smartphones at home, turning functionalities off or putting their smartphones to flight mode, or even buying dumb phones only for use in public. Several participants said they would never use public Wi-Fi. Others decided to turn off Bluetooth and Wi-Fi on their phones when leaving the house after seeing the signs about tracking in the shopping mall. One participant mentioned one could simply not have a smartphone subscription to avoid resale of mobile network data.

“Yes, I have nothing to hide, but I just don’t want everything to be available.”

While some participants spontaneously mentioned data subject rights accorded in the GDPR, like the right to access and the right to erasure, many were unaware of them (as the section

above on transparency shows). Participants also mentioned sometimes that most people would not be aware of such rights.

As for more proactive engagement in the smart city, several participants reported having used the app Fix My Street. One participant noted that reaction times can vary dramatically; sometimes the issue gets fixed instantly, sometimes you never hear again about what you reported.

5. Evaluation of the method

The workshops were evaluated with the participants and with the smart city administrators by way of a short paper evaluation form. Based on those evaluation, it seems that the workshops were mostly experienced as useful, instructive, clear, and informative by participants. This may show that the methodology is indeed a good way to inform citizens over smart city aspects, but also to facilitate interaction between citizens and decision-makers. The positive feedback from the decision-makers that participated in one of the walks seems to confirm the value of the methodology for mutual learning.

Interestingly, it seems that the (new) information received did indeed also raise the concerns about data processing's in general. At the same time, the information did also seem to raise the acceptance of smart city solutions slightly (most participants stated that they are neither more nor less convinced after the workshops. The results for the citizen participants were:

	Completel y disagree				Completel y agree
The workshop was useful.	1	0	1	3	13
I have learned something during the workshop.	0	0	0	6	11
The information was clear to me.	0	0	1	8	9
The information was sufficient for me.	0	0	3	7	8
I would recommend the workshop too friends.	0	1	4	3	10

The last two questions for citizens addressed the processing of personal data in the smart city:

	Less concerned				More concerned
Are you more concerned or less concerned about the collection of personal data in cities than before?	0	0	6	9	3
	Less convinced				More convinced

Are you more convinced or less convinced of the advantages of the smart city than before?	0	1	12	3	2
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The smart city administrators received slightly different questions. Their responses were:

	Completely disagree			Completely agree	
The walkshop was useful.	0	0	0	1	3
The walkshop is useful to involve citizens in smart city decision-making.	0	0	0	1	3
The walkshop was interesting.	0	0	0	2	2
I have learned something during the walkshop.	0	0	0	2	2

To open questions about their ideas for the potential uses of walkshops, they answered:

- “Raising awareness among citizens or city employees. Making data protection more concrete for them.”
- “To create awareness and public discussion for all citizens, stakeholders and city administrators.”

One smart city administrator suggested improving the walkshop by getting more information about the purpose of the data collected by the different devices.

There was an additional question to the smart city administrators about any changes in their level of conviction about the advantages of smart cities (the same as the last question to citizens), but none reported any changes.

6. Discussion and preliminary conclusions

Four walks with a total of twenty-eight participants form a small sample of the Brussels population, which moreover came about through self-selection and shows a certain 'bias' in composition. This can be partly explained by the fact that only those interested in the walkshop topics will register, and a certain level of digital skills was required to register online for the walkshop. It is therefore doubtful that these participants are representative of the general interest of the Brussels population in being involved. If the aim of the walkshops is to engage a wider range of citizens and collect a diversity of perspectives on collecting smart city data, the selection bias must be overcome methodologically. Further research may explore various remedies, such as targeting marginalized groups specifically and recruiting participants on the spot rather than online. Any conclusions and recommendations should therefore be viewed with some reservations.

Nevertheless, the potential seems to exist to involve interested citizens in decision-making about data collection in public space, perhaps as representatives of the population and as ambassadors for more widely supported smart city projects. Directly involving city dwellers in the decision-making process by walking with them offers several benefits to decision makers. By putting the feet of decision-makers on the ground next to the feet of citizens, experiencing

the environment in which problems arise and talking about it with people who have direct experience with the problem, ideas can arise for new solutions.

As in the other cities, cameras have been a prevalent topic during the workshops in Brussels. Whether camera monitoring is effective or not, the workshops in Brussels showed there was a relatively high degree of scepticism among the participants towards the necessity of cameras in public space, which is not unlike our findings in Ghent and Leuven. This can be partly due to biases in the recruitment method for these workshops but may not be an all too uncommon perception in society. What is clear in any case, is that there is little communication about the effectiveness of camera monitoring. Citizens would appreciate proof of actual effectiveness, especially regarding safety and security, as they are currently judging camera monitoring based on anecdotes and disappointing personal experiences.

It is noteworthy that the GDPR's right to being informed could be used by data controllers to prevent several issues and negative perceptions before they arise. More proactive communication about purposes and results, not only on information signs but also in the press, could potentially address these negative perceptions.

While the groups of participants cannot be said to be representative for the entire population of Brussels, the results on the right to be informed and the right to access among generally knowledgeable citizens do suggest that these rights need further support. Although participants acknowledged they should know more about the personal data that is processed, at least some citizens seem to avoid paying attention to information provided due to a fear of paranoia.

A self-protection mechanism that has been mentioned as a sort of last resort by several participants that were more critical about the processing of their personal data in public space was the full avoidance of any tracking technology: airplane mode on the phone, phones without e.g. wifi or Bluetooth sensor, or no phone at all. An interesting aspect in this regard is also apparent differences between age groups when it comes to concerns and risk perceptions regarding data processing. During the workshops, it was mentioned several times by different participants, who were mostly older, that younger generations may not at all be as concerned as "older generations". To follow-up on, we manage to organise a walk with a group of bachelor students of the VUB. The input from this group seems that the age difference might indeed play a role: in the group of students most were much more accepting of the data processing. This possible difference, and the effects it may have on fundamental rights to privacy, is something that deserves careful attention in further research.

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